

Knowledge and Attitude of Senior Secondary School Students to Strabismus in an Urban Town in South Western Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This cross-sectional descriptive survey was carried out to determine the knowledge of strabismus and attitudes of Secondary school students in Sagamu Local Government area (LGA) about strabismus. A multistage sampling technique was used to select three secondary schools in Sagamu LGA for the research. A validated semi-structured self-administered questionnaire for the purpose of the research was used to collect data. Approval was obtained from the Zonal Education Office of the State Ministry of Education, Science & Technology and the Principals of the selected schools. Data was analyzed using SPSS statistical package version 20. Knowledge score and attitude scores were calculated. A total of 1082 students were studied. There were 486(45.2%) males and 593 females. Their age ranges from 10years to 21years with a mean of 15.3+1.48years. Five hundred and eleven (46.7%) respondents were able to define strabismus correctly as eye turn. About forty percent think strabismus can be outgrown. Fifty percent of respondents would not marry someone with strabismus. Knowledge score was less than 50% in 97.7% of respondents.

We concluded that knowledge and awareness of strabismus is low among the senior secondary school students. Intensified health education and awareness campaign to increase knowledge by Ophthalmologists should be embarked upon. This will also increase uptake of treatment

Keywords: Attitude, Nigeria, School, Secondary, Strabismus, Urban

INTRODUCTION

Strabismus otherwise called Squint is a pathological condition which commonly develops as a result of abnormality in the development of binocular single vision with resultant abnormal appearance from eye

deviation. The prevalence of strabismus in the developed countries is 2-5%^[1,2], whereas studies done among primary school children in Ilorin and Benin in Nigeria recorded a prevalence of 0.14% and 1.89% respectively^[3,4]. Children

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and adults with strabismus often suffer from several psychosocial and emotional consequences such as poor self- image, negative social bias, ridicule at school, ostracization, depression, anger and outrage, increased social anxiety, poor interpersonal relationship, inhibition and poor job opportunities in adults^[5,6]. Rohit *et al* found that strabismus places a heavy burden on tertiary care centers and results in a significant financial and socio-economic burden on the society and individuals in terms of management^[7]. Also it has been reported that strabismic patients have impaired visual function because they often have subnormal binocular summation and inhibition^[8]. However, there is no data on the burden of strabismus in Nigeria to the best of our knowledge. This high burden is probably what has led to the high uptake of treatment in the developed countries and in India whereas it is very low in the developing countries.

Studies have also shown that uncorrected strabismus affect the quality of life of not only the children with strabismus, but also their family members^[6]. Adolescents and youth are usually more likely to be impacted by the negative psychosocial effect particularly in terms of marriage and job opportunities. Also, the health- seeking behavior of people is related to their knowledge of a disease therefore a good knowledge of strabismus in the adolescent may result in improve uptake of treatment in those with strabismus. Attitude to a disease and vaccines has been found to be a predictor of immunization uptake and this could be same for strabismus^[9].

Little is known about the attitudes and behaviors of adolescents to Strabismus in Nigeria. This study therefore aimed at determining the knowledge and attitude of Senior Secondary School Students in Sagamu Local Government Area (LGA) of Nigeria to Strabismus. It is hoped that the findings from this study will provide a baseline data for further studies and provide evidence-based data for health planners to plan improved health care.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Location: Sagamu LGA, one of the 20 local Governments of Ogun State which is located in the South Western Zone of the Country. The LGA has a mixed population.

Study population: Senior secondary school students attending public secondary schools in Sagamu Local Government Area were recruited into the study. SS3 students were exempted from participating in the study because their final examinations were on-going and each of them only go to school when they have papers thus unavailable. The sample was collected over 6 weeks

Study design- A cross sectional study was carried out among students attending public senior secondary schools in Sagamu LGA.

Sample size determination: Using the formula for descriptive studies and assuming a prevalence of 50% (since to the best of our knowledge, no such study has been carried out on the subject matter in South-Western Nigeria), as well as a non-response rate of 10%, a sample size of 420 was calculated. However, this was exceeded and 1082 students were recruited into the study.

Sampling technique: Multi-stage sampling technique was used for selection of study participants. The first stage involved the selection of three (3) wards from the fifteen (15) existing wards in Sagamu LGA by simple random sampling. The second stage involved the selection of one secondary school in each of the pre-selected wards also by simple random sampling. Each of these school had both senior and junior arms. Third stage involved the selection of 3 arms from the five existing arms of SS1 and SS2 in each school. These arms served as clusters. All consenting students in the selected arms were recruited into the study.

Study instrument: A validated; semi structured, self-administered questionnaire was used for data collection among the study participants. The questionnaire obtained information on socio-demographic data, knowledge and attitude of respondents to strabismus.

Data management: Data was checked for completeness and accuracy after each day's field work. Data was

analyzed with IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. Knowledge score was calculated on a scale of 100%, with a good knowledge being a score of 50% and above, while a score of less than 50% was graded as poor. Attitude score was also calculated and graded as good and poor. A score of 50% was graded as good while that less than 50% was graded as poor. Descriptive statistics were calculated and reported as frequencies, proportions, means and standard deviation. Chi square test was used to test for association between categorical variables, with level of significance (p) set at <0.05.

Ethical considerations: Approval was obtained from the Zonal Education Office of the State Ministry of Education, Science & Technology. Approval was also obtained from the Principals of the selected schools. This study followed the ethical standards issued by the Nuremberg Code and the Declaration of Helsinki on research in humans. Informed (written) consent was obtained from study participants. Participation was fully voluntary and respondents were free to withdraw from the study if they so wished. Strict confidentiality was ensured throughout the course of the study.

RESULTS

There were 489(45.2%) males and 593(54.8%) females with a male female ratio of 1:1.2. Age ranged from 10-21 years with a mean of 15.3 ± 1.48 years. There were more Christians and more students were in SS2 (Table 1). Five hundred and seventy-one (52.8%) have heard of squint before while five hundred and twelve have not. Of these 144 (25.2%) heard from medical practitioners, 90 (15.8%) from media, 75 (13.1%) from family members, 71 (12.4%) from teachers.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of respondents

	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	489	45.2
Female	593	54.8
Religion		
Christianity	720	66.5
Islam	358	33.1
Traditional	4	0.4
Level of study		
SS 1	525	48.5
SS 2	547	50.6
SS3	10	0.9
Age (years)		
10 -12	25	2.1
13 -15	568	52.5
16 -18	470	43.4
19-21	21	1.9

Knowledge of strabismus

511(47.2%) correctly defined squint as eye turn. Five hundred and forty-two (50.1%) think sitting too close to television can cause squint. Two hundred and seventy-one (25.1%) do not know that squint can be treated while 40.9% think squint can be outgrown (Table 2)

Table 2: Knowledge of strabismus by respondents

What is squint	Frequency	Percentage
Squeezing eyes to see	213	19.7
Eye turn/deviation of the eye	511	47.2
Don't know	358	33.1
Causes of squint		
Sitting too close to TV	542	50.1
Hereditary/congenital	244	22.6
Injury to the eyes	168	15.5
Unknown	151	14.0
Refusal to wear glasses	122	11.3
Wearing spectacles	121	11.2
Reading too much	87	8.0
Others	58	5.4
Witchcraft	44	4.1
Can squint be treated?		
Yes	667	61.6
No	148	13.7
Don't know	267	24.7

Attitude to strabismus

One hundred and seventy- six respondents (16.2%) would not play with someone with squint. Of this 59(33.5%) would not because of the fear of contacting squint. Five hundred and forty three (50.5%) and five hundred and twenty three (48.3%) would not marry someone with squint or allow their siblings marry someone with squint (Table 3). Though majority will advise their friends with strabismus to see a Doctor, there are still some misconceptions as 2.5% will advise the person to see an herbalist and 1.9% would advise that it will resolve spontaneously.

Table 3: Attitude of respondents to strabismus

	Frequency	Percentage
Play with someone having strabismus		
Yes	751	69.4
No	176	16.3
Undecided	155	14.3
Marry someone with strabismus		
Yes	297	27.4
No	543	50.2
Don't know	242	22.4
Brother/sister to marry someone with strabismus		
Yes	312	28.8
No	523	48.3
Don't know	247	22.8

Effect of strabismus

Five hundred and ninety-three (54.3%) felt one consequence of squint is reduce vision, 181(16.7%) cosmetic blemish and 518(47.9%) psychological trauma (Table 4).

Table IV: Response of respondents on the effect of squint

Effect of squint	Yes (%)	No (%)
Reduced vision	592 (54.7)	490(45.3)
Psychological trauma	518 (47.9)	563(52.0)
Cosmetic blemish	181(16.7)	901(83.3)
Problems with marriage	96(8.9)	986(91.1)
Reduced vision & Cosmetic blemish	138(12.8)	944(87.3)
Reduced vision and psychological trauma	356(32.9)	726(67.1)

The knowledge score was less than 50% in 1070(97.7%) respondents with a poor grade in 1045(95.9%). Perception score was $\geq 50\%$ in 758 respondents. Perception grade was good in 755(68.9%). Only the class of respondent was found to be statically significant in relation to knowledge among these students.

DISCUSSION

This study showed that about 52.8% of respondents have heard of strabismus indicating that awareness of teenagers in this community is low as compared to Getal et al who found that all their participants had heard of strabismus before [5] and Isawunmi et al who found 75% awareness among eye clinic patients [10]. Also awareness of strabismus was found to be better in a Focused group discussion carried out in another local Government area close to the area for this present study by same author [11]. The fact that less than fifty percent of respondent were the ones able to define strabismus correctly also corroborated this. Intensified health education by health workers especially during school health clinic visits will help increase awareness.

The knowledge of strabismus was also found to be low as about 50% thought it is caused by sitting too close to television while another 40% thought it cannot be treated. This is similar to the findings of the findings of other researchers [5, 10]. Despite the fact that knowledge score was poor it is worthy to note that secondary school students still exhibited negative psychosocial responses towards strabismus as about half of the respondents will not play

with colleagues who have strabismus and not marry or allow their siblings to marry someone with strabismus. This confirms the findings of other workers^[6]. Studies have also shown that strabismus plays an important role in selecting a partner for adults and in selecting a playmate for children^[12,13]. This is however different from the finding of Bodunde et al in a focus group discussion^[11]. It has also been shown that quality of life to psychosocial effect is low in people with strabismus including teenagers^[14,15,16].

One of the prerequisites of health-seeking behavior is knowledge of disease and their symptoms. The low level of knowledge may be one reason why many do not seek medical intervention for their strabismus and also explain why some parents decline intervention for their children. We therefore suggest conducting programs to increase awareness on the consequences of strabismus and ways of treatment among youths in the LGA.

Majority of the respondents didn't know that strabismus can result in reduced vision, psychological trauma, problems of marriage, cosmetic blemish etc. This could be one of the reasons why uptake of treatment for strabismus is low unlike in the developed countries where several reports have shown these as consequences^[6]. It has been suggested that individuals with strabismus are adversely affected in many aspects of their lives, including finding a partner, job prospects and interaction with peers^[12,13]. These effects will impact more on adolescent than children as they are the groups that need peer approval more.

We conclude that the knowledge and awareness of strabismus is low among secondary school students in Sagamu. This may be the factor impacting on the level of presentation and uptake of treatment for strabismus in the environment. Intensified health education and awareness campaign will help increase awareness and knowledge.

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